

Research Symposium: New Regional Order

Is a New Regional Order Emerging in the Middle East?

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Israel's response to the Hamas attack on October 7, 2023, has reopened old wounds and deepened tensions, with major implications for the United States. Israel pursued a war of annihilation in Gaza, aimed at eradicating Hamas, resulting in the death of thousands of Palestinian civilians and the destruction of the hospitals, schools, and infrastructure. Israel's military operation has been criticized widely by many international agencies as disproportionate and unwarranted. South Africa brought a case of genocide against Israel to the International Court of Justice, a case that is deemed "plausible" by the UN's top judges despite Israel's protests (Casciani 2024). In December 2024 Amnesty International issued its own report on the war and condemned it as genocidal (Amnesty International 2024). Throughout the international outcry against the way Israel was conducting its war in Gaza, the United States remained steadfast in its support of Israel and repeated Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu's mantra of self-defense. This position has done enormous damage to the US image in the Middle East.

Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates and Egypt, key regional players, already had con-

cerns about the reliability of the United States as a guarantor of their security before the current crisis. They were unhappy with the nuclear deal with Iran, negotiated during Barak Obama's presidency in 2015. They complained that it gave Iran a free hand to pursue an interventionist regional policy to their detriment. In spite of assurances from Washington, these states felt sidestepped. The region was shocked again in 2020 when the United States, this time during Donald Trump's presidency, negotiated an unconditional withdrawal of US troops from Afghanistan. The US exit took place in 2021 during Joe Biden's presidency. The Taliban rolled into Kabul within days. After investing blood and treasure for two decades, Washington gave up Afghanistan to the very forces it had vowed to fight, leaving its allies to scurry for safety. These experiences have not been reassuring for Arab leaders who have traditionally relied on the United States for their security.

Washington's unconditional support for Israel during the Gaza war has further strengthened the view in the region that the priorities of the United States do not necessarily match regional interests. This realization has given impetus to two trends: search for security

diversification and a growing awareness of the need for self-sufficiency.

The perception of US disengagement from the Middle East has opened the door for China (and, to a lesser extent, Russia) to step in and fill the void. China has pursued greater engagement with the Middle East through its Belt and Road Initiative. Major investments in infrastructure without asking for political reforms or expecting conformity with a normative framework have made China an attractive partner. Beijing's insistence on the sanctity of state sovereignty and the projected image of non-interference with the internal affairs of other states presents a sharp contrast with the history of US involvement in the Middle East. The United States was widely seen as trying to remake the region in its own image. This, of course, caricaturizes facts. The reality of the Middle East experience with the United States has been far more complex. Yet these impressions have taken hold of the political imagination, and China has been keen to take advantage of them. China's quiet diplomacy to bring the Saudis and Iranians to the table in 2023 – ending seven years of diplomatic rupture – was a significant win for Beijing (Berg 2023). While China is careful not to over-extend its reach, it has signaled its interest in upholding regional security through bilateral strategic agreements with Iran, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and UAE.

At the same time, there is a growing realization among rich Arab states that they need to take charge of their own national security and reduce reliance on great powers. This realization has fed growing investment in security and the purchase of military hardware as well as diplomatic efforts at tension-reduction (Lucenete 2024). Saudi and UAE overtures to Iran in recent years are significant indicators

of a paradigm-shift, reflecting a realization in Riyadh and Abu Dhabi that hostility towards Iran, pursued by President Trump in his first term and resumed in his second, breeds further regional instability and detracts from major economic development and diversification plans.

The Middle East regional order is in flux. The reliability and primacy of the United States are in question; China has sought to take advantage of this opportunity, especially in the oil-rich Persian Gulf littoral states to satisfy its energy needs. At the same time, regional players are searching for self-reliance. This is most evident in the growing diplomatic relations by Arab states with Iran, a recognition that isolating Iran would be counter-productive for regional stability. This may herald a new regional order, one in which regional players exercise greater autonomy in their relations with the United States and diversify their security partnerships to gain leverage and expand their scope of decision-making.♦

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